

Implementation of Sentimental Analysis and Data Visualization in Hotel Management system using Natural Language Processing

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Abstract— This paper is delivered to calculate the sentimental analysis and visualize the customer feedback about the hotel services and other facilities provided by the hotel in a hotel management system using natural language processing. It helps the management of the hotel to upgrade their service and find the customer expectations about the stay and services. It provides anonymity to the customer. That is no one knows the identity of the customer who provided the feedback. The feedback entered by the customer is only visible to the administration team of the hotel. The manager can give correct instructions to the staff to enhance their service according to the feedback provided by the customer. The proposed system will also give a visualization of the feedback data

Keywords—NLP, flask, data visualization, sentimental analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

As the days go the number of tourists and travel enthusiasts is increasing, they prefer to stay in good and well-maintained hotels all around the place, a good hotel is family-friendly and should be enjoyed with friends. The facilities provided by the hotel are very remarkable in the mind of the customers and it will lead to negative or positive feedback according to the facilities provided by the hotel and also depends on the service. The positive feedback from the customers enhances the hotel business by spreading positive reviews to their friends and family. So that makes a good impression on the hotel and grows its reputation of the hotel. Negative feedback will impact just the opposite of positive feedback and it will ruin the organization's reputation, So the feedback provided by the customer is very much important to an analyzer hotel business, and also it will help to improve the service and guide the staff by the managers.

The advanced form of feedback analysis is sentimental analysis. The proposed system the sentimental analysis is implemented by using natural language processing. As we know data visualization helps to make more understanding above data hence the visualization of the feedback gathered from the customers is depicted using a chart in the proposed system. For sentimental analysis, we employ Natural Language Processing (NLP), a field of computer science and, more specifically, a subfield of artificial intelligence (AI), which deals with enabling computers to comprehend written and spoken language in a manner like to that of humans.

A. Nature of Natural Language Processing

Machine translation from one language to another. Classification, indexing, and summarization of written documents. Identify sentiment and opinion in text and voice-based data.

B. Sentimental Analysis

Sentiment analysis is the process of identifying, extracting, quantifying, and studying emotional states and important information using natural language processing, text analysis, computational linguistics, and biometrics.

C. Chart.js

It's free open-source JavaScript for data visualization. Chart.js has eight types of charts: bar, line, area, pie, bubble, radar, polar, and scatter

II. SENTIMENTAL ANALYSIS – NATURAL LANGUAGE PROCESSING

Sentiment analysis, as the name implies, entails determining the viewpoint or feeling underlying a circumstance. In essence, it is examining and identifying the feelings and purposes hidden in text, speech, and other forms of communication. Although we speak many different languages as humans, each one is only a medium or way for us to express ourselves. And everything we say has a meaning to us. It could be positive, negative or both.

Suppose you have a fast food chain that sells a variety of foods such as hamburgers, pizza, sandwiches, and milkshakes. They created a website that sells groceries and customers will be able to order groceries from his website and even leave reviews such as B. Do you like or dislike food?

User Review 1: I love this cheese sandwich, it's so good.

User Review 2: This chicken burger tastes so bad.

User Review 3: I ordered this pizza today.

The first review is positive and the company is doing well.

The second review is negative and the company should look into the burger section.

The third can be considered a neutral statement because it does not indicate whether the customer is satisfied.

From the above reviews, we can conclude that the company needs to focus more on producing and promoting

sandwiches and improving the quality of its burgers if it wants to increase overall sales.

A. Data Visualization

Data visualization helps to make much more understanding of the obtained data and it is easy to make wise decisions according to the information obtained from the conclusion. It is the graphical depiction of the data. It may be charts or other types of visual measures.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

A natural language processing model for sentimental analysis and data visualisation is what the defined model aims to create. Positive and negative input should be able to be categorised by the model. A training dataset is used to train the algorithm or model, and consumer feedback is used to generate the test data. By exposing the model to more datasets during training, we can improve its accuracy. As a result, a model that may be applied to feedback analysis is produced.

The feedback provided by the customers remains anonymous. That is it is not possible to identify who provided the feedback.

The steps required for the proposed model :

1. Collection of data
2. Pre-processing
3. Model Generating
4. Model Analysis
5. Final output

Data Collection

Customers can enter their feedback after checking out the room and it will be stored in the database. This data is used for sentimental analysis with the help of natural language processing.

Data preprocessing

It is the process done in all machine learning techniques It includes data cleaning, transformation, and reducing the data. The main aim of the process is to make our model effective. In order to make our classification accurate, the data is processed

1. *Data Cleaning* – First step in the data process. Noisy data is removed in this process
2. *Stop words removal* – The unimportant data and the data which is repeating are also removed. That is no impact on the result after removing the stopwords
3. *Splitting of Data* – Data splitting into training and test data sets follows data cleansing, with the training data set being used to improve the performance of the data.
4. *Model Generating* –Generating the model using the training data sets and it is used for processing the data
5. *Model Analysis* –Analysing the performance of the generated model

6. *Final output* –Generating the final output using our developed system

Diagram 1

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

1. *Import the necessary packages*

```

from email.policy import default
from sqlite3 import Cursor
from unittest.mock import DEFAULT
from flask import Flask, request, render_template
from sklearn.feature_extraction.text import TfidfVectorizer
from sklearn.metrics.pairwise import cosine_similarity
from flask_mysql import MySQL
from vaderSentiment.vaderSentiment import SentimentIntensityAnalyzer
import nltk
    
```

```
from string import punctuation
import re
from nltk.corpus import stopwords
from flask_mysql import MySQL
```

2. Getting data from the user

User can enter their feedback through the user interface

Figure 1

3. Convert to lowercase

Conversion of the feedback gets rid of unhelpful portions of the feedback, or noise in it, by transforming the entire text or data to lowercase

4. Remove stopwords

The unimportant data and the data which is repeating are also removed. That is no impact on the result after removing the stopwords

4. Final result

Figure 2

4. Data visualisation

The visualization of the feedback depicts more clear idea about the taken feedback and it is easy to make wise decisions according to the information obtained from the

conclusion. It is the graphical depiction of the data. It may be charts or other types of visual measures.

Figure 3

V. CONCLUSION

This paper provides a method for analysing the feedback provided by the customers or guest who stayed in the hotel or used a service provided by the hotel. The analysis done in the proposed model is sentimental analysis with the help of natural language processing. The system also provides anonymity for users who enters the feedback about the service. This allows the users to provide genuine feedback since the identity is hidden.

The system becomes more effective with increasing the dataset and it will more accurate. Increasing the data set can be consider as future work reference.

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